

COMMUNITY RADIO AND SUSTENANCE OF MARITAL PEACE IN EDO STATE

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Abstract

This study was carried out to investigate the relevance of community radio in sustaining marital peace in Edo State. The study was anchored on Family System Theory. Survey research design was adopted in this study. It has a population of 4,777,000 residents of Edo State drawn from the eighteen Local Government Areas of the State. From the population, a sample size of 385 gotten via Online Australian Calculator was adopted. The instrument used for data collection was structured questionnaire and data collected were presented and analyzed using descriptive data analysis method. Findings of this study revealed that: majority of the residents of Edo State were highly aware of the use of community radio in sustaining marital peace in the State, most of respondents agreed that community radio usually broadcasted family/marital peace oriented programmes and campaigns and the extent to which community radio contributed in sustaining marital peace is still low in Edo State. The study recommended that community radio stations in Edo State should involve digital and social media platforms in disseminating information on sustainable marriage peace in the State. Also, marriage counselors, church leaders and peace communication experts should partner with community radio on communicating marital peace in Edo State. **Key Words:** Community, Marriage, Peace, Radio, Sustenance.

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1 Introduction

Over the years, radio has continued to serve as a medium of mass communication. It is an electronic wireless device which serves as a channel of receiving and disseminating information or messages through air waves from the source to the target consumer. Nna (2020) reveals that it is a specialized mass medium with considerable local programming directed to specialized local audience and it is less expensive to programme. As a broadcasting station, it serves a specific section of a society known as a community, which is a collection of people, usually living in the same area, with common interests that include having a common history, traditions and cultural background of the community (Kasoma, 2002). It has the ability to deliver well packaged programmes to a defined geographical and demographic target audience, and could be described as a community radio that serves as number one communication medium for the Nigerian society.

The emergence of community radio in Nigeria has been a welcome development in accessing and communicating with rural communities. It was developed to meet the communication cum information needs of Nigerian communities. It is a small-scale radio station owned and operated by a community or its representative to be heard, informed and become more decisive agent for its own sake when it comes to any contextual issues (Mefalopulos, 2005). Radio has equally grown both in structure, content and outreach by

providing regular and updated dosages of information on the happenings in the society. More so, it provides tremendous opportunities for people to share their views, ideas, and messages the welfare and overall development of the rural dwellers.

One of the important aspects of the roles of community radio is provision of information, messages and programmes on family cum marital living for the maintenance of peace, unity and progress. Marriage is an indispensable institution that forms and builds societies. It is a legally recognized and socially accepted partnership, typically involving two different individual of opposite sex. Egbo, Asogwa and Agbo-Peters (2020) see marriage is seen as an institution to satisfy physical, psychological, social, cultural and economic needs of man and woman, which permits them to establish a stable relationship with each other. Marriage brings joy and happiness to the society and honour to those who are in it. It is seen as union between a man and a woman who loves each other and has agreed to leave together as husband and wife, with legal backing, through contemporary way or performing traditional rites (Makinde, Azorundu, Adeoye, & Abodunrin, 2021).

Marriage is governed by laws, norms, conventions, beliefs, and attitudes that specify the spouses' rights and obligations and grant status to their children. It is a legally and socially sanctioned union, usually between a man and a woman that is regulated by laws, rules, customs, beliefs and attitudes that prescribe the rights and duties of the partners and accords status to their children (Encyclopaedia Britannica, 2025). These ingredients include such attributes as commitment, communication, children, finances, respect, emotional bonding, religion, parents' marriage, love, intimacy and so on. Research has shown that having a long-lasting marriage is very important to people and has a great impact on their health and general life satisfaction and stability (Bradbury, 2014).

However, Lenthal (2019) explains the need for marital peace as the condition of a steady, well-balanced and healthy relationship between husband and wife, irrespective of any misunderstanding that may arise between them in the course of their discussion. Marital peace can be seen as the endurance of a marriage due to the cooperation of both husband and wife. It manifests in a situation where husband and wife love each other, get along well, share common goal and interests, enjoy each other's company, and have fun together. Conversely, lack of communication among couples may diminish intimacy between them. Communication on marriage involves the exchange of information and messages between couples through spoken words, written words, symbols, body gestures, and facial expressions.

Communication within the family is widely recognized as a fundamental element in the development and maintenance of healthy marital relationships. It ought to be a vital factor in maintaining a satisfying marital peace. It is therefore on this premise that this study was carried out to ascertain the relevance of community radio, specifically the Edo State Broadcasting Service (EBS) in sustaining marital peace in Edo State.

2 Statement of the Problem

There is no doubt of the existence of studies on marriage and its related issues in Edo State. For instance, Osagie & Godson (2024) studied "Contributing Factors of Marriage Dissolution in Oredo Local Government Area, Edo State, Nigeria". Egharevba & Omosuvbe (2021) also did a study on "Role of the Extended Family on Marital Instability in Egor Local Government Area, Edo State, Nigeria" while Awosan, Iroye and Okolo (2023) studied "Spousal communication on marital stability and productivity in Nigeria" and (Makinde, Azorundu, Adeoye, & Abodunrin, (2021) on the "Principles of Marriage". These, among others revealed the importance of marital in Edo State of Nigeria.

Unfortunately, available studies on marriage in Edo State have not addressed the issue of mass media and marital peace as an intellectual approach of addressing incidences of marital problems such as lack of misunderstanding, poverty, third-party interference from in-laws, infidelity, and incompatibility, leading to conflicts, emotional stress, and separation or divorce. These problems can negatively impact the couples, children and contributing to delinquency and psychological issues, and often lead to instability and crisis

within the marriage cum family.

As a result of the above problem, this study was carried out to ascertain the relevance of community radio, using Edo State Broadcasting Service (EBS), in sustaining marital peace in Edo State. It is believed that this study will advance knowledge in appraising the contributions of community radio in building and maintaining marital peace among couples and families in the State.

3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the relevance of community radio in sustaining marital peace in Edo State. Three specific objectives are:

1. To ascertain the level of Edo State residents' access to Edo State Broadcasting Service community radio messages on marital peace in the State.
2. To find out the role of Edo State Broadcasting Service community radio on marital peace in Edo State.
3. To ascertain the effectiveness Edo State Broadcasting Service community radio in sustaining marital peace in Edo State.

4 Research Questions

1. What is the level of Edo State residents' access to EBS community radio messages on marital peace in the State?
2. What is the role of EBS community radio on marital peace in Edo State?
3. What is the effectiveness EBS community radio in sustaining marital peace in Edo State?

5 Significance of the Study

This study centred on relevance of Edo State Broadcasting Service community radio in sustaining marital peace in Edo State. It provided current and relevant information on sustaining marital peace in Edo State through the use of community radio. Such valuable facts and information can be useful to marriages, families and radio stations in Edo State. In like manner, the study provided theoretical and practical facts to future scholars, policy makers and peace agencies including the state Government for managing related issues of marital peace. In the same vein, this study forms a reference document to community radio stations and library sources so as advance this field of knowledge in Edo State.

6 Review of Related Literature

6.1 Community Radio and its Functions

Community radio is as a radio station established to provide services to its host community. It is seen in this perspective as an authentic tool in ensuring early warning and monitoring signal, mediation, facilitating and perfecting alternative dispute resolution mechanisms, and contributing significantly to societal orientation on issues of diversity that are often the cause of conflicts and violence when poorly managed. This could be achieved through the education role of community radio. Community radio is described as a credible socializing agent that contributes meaningfully in peace education. It could promote local identity, character and create diversity of voices and opinions, encourage open dialogue and the democratic process, and promote civil society, good governance and professional responsibility (Alumuku, 2006). All these roles could

contribute immensely to bring about an effective education that could promote peace and shun all tendencies of violence and disunity.

The basic premise of community radio according to Vega, Tapias & Pérez (2019) focuses on nonprofit, participatory, and media made by and for a local audience, providing a variety of educational and entertainment programs to facilitate community development. Radio has become a specialized medium with considerable local programming directed to specialized and local audiences and it is much less expensive to programme local radio than to programme local television. This type of radio also proved to be a sustainable and interactive space for poor and marginalized populations to be heard and informed, form their opinions, and become more decisive agents in their development (McKay, 2010 & Wabwire, 2013).

Unlike other forms of mass media, the use of community radio by the government and other agencies is linking the rural communities to the urban communities and at the same time channel the happenings – events, programmes and development in the urban to the rural areas. Thus, it is used to create a two way information flow between the two extremes. The government is the major user of radio to connect its rural people to what they are doing, or about to do or have done for them (Okwechime, 2007). They (rural people) do not only constitute the largest portion of the population but also have a lot of human angle and interesting activities, such as their agricultural, socio-cultural and rural political programmes.

Radio is therefore a busy mass medium, with a lot of roles and functions it owes the society. Aliede (2003) calls it a tool for journalism education, enlightenment, mobilization, cultural propagation and entertainment. Radio also promotes economic development, stimulates political participation and arouses national consciousness and unity. Thus, previous reports have shown that radio performs the following functions: information dissemination, education of the masses, entertainment, mobilization, sensitization and motivation of the target audience to respond to a particular message. Once the audience has access to the medium, communication becomes a right. Akpan (2000) observes, people cannot live and share ideas, interact and peacefully progress without communicating about themselves and their needs.

6.2 Concept of Marital Peace

The term "marital" relates to marriage, while "peace" means the absence of conflict and emotional imbalance. Igbino (2023) shares the idea that marital peace can be understood as a situation where couples remain legally married and live together in harmony, without separation or persistent conflict. It reflects a state of marital success or satisfaction. Marital peace refers to the state of living in harmony, understanding one another and emotional closeness that exists between spouses. It is vital for building a strong and satisfying marriage, as it contributes to the emotional well-being and happiness of the family. He further explains that a healthy and successful marriage depends on how husbands and wives relate to each other, how well they support one another, and the level of their commitment to the relationship (Igbino, 2023).

Marriage is not just a union but a journey that requires wisdom, honesty, loyalty, and trust. Trust allows couples to stay calm and united even during difficult times (Punch Newspaper, 2023). According to Nwosu (2022), marital peace is when the normal daily life and activities of the family continue without disruption, supporting both the emotional and physical well-being of all family members. Also, marital peace as a stable and successful marriage made possible by important values such as love, care, trust, acceptance, and tolerance. These qualities help couples deal with emotional challenges and keep their relationships strong. In essence, marital peace is built on mutual respect, emotional connection, and a shared belief in unity, which are all necessary for a fulfilling and lasting marriage.

In Nigeria, the rate at which marital couples experience divorce is quite alarming. Many families have been and some are still seriously at war with themselves simply because they fail to arrest, manage or resolve conflicting issues between couples or families. The marital instability and conflicts between couples may not be unconnected with the harsh economic and social realities coupled with other factors like in-law interference, incompatibility and unwholesome desires of one or both couples. The negative impact of the problem in marriages in Nigeria and the study area particularly is better imagined. The extended family for ages has been the formidable mediator and arbiter in all family problems and squabbles including settling

of marital conflict. Egharevba & Omosuvb (2021) observe that the extent to which the extended family is still relevant in a marital settlement is to some extent based on speculation in the modern complex and cosmopolitan Nigerian society.

Egharevba & Omosuvb (2021) reveal that dissolved marriages bring about unwanted expenses on both sides. This is truer when litigation is involved. The individual from dissolved marriage may use his or her money to engage lawyers, corrupt the police and/or buy witness. Dissolved marriage creates enmity between individual and groups and strains existing relationships. The children of dissolved couples are likely to lack proper care from both parents and this may lead to breeding of misfits in the society. When peaceful atmosphere is replaced with chaos in marriage, the consequences are usually grievous. It results in marital instability, marriage separation, divorce or even death of the couple. This has serious effects on the home, family, children of the marriage, society at large (Ojukwu, 2016).

6.3 Communicating Marital Peace

Communication is critical to the success of every marriage. Most marriages may breakdown due to lack of communication. Communication affects every issue in marriage. We must talk about money, conflict and every other area in the relationship, but effective communication never happens by accident, it's always on purpose. Amah (2023) reveals that effective communication is vital in building a strong, healthy, and lasting marriage in Igboland. He further explains that effective Communication in marriage in Igbo land encourages understanding, builds trust, resolves conflicts, improves intimacy, and encourages growth and foster teamwork among the couples.

Communication is a key aspect of every marriage, as it allows couples to express their thoughts, opinions, and desires to each other. Effective communication in marriage encourages couples to build trust, intimacy, and understanding, while lack of communication can lead to misunderstandings, conflicts, and lack of trust. In the past, communication between married adults was often restricted by cultural and social norms that placed a great emphasis on gender roles and power dynamics within the relationship. This led to a lack of openness and honesty in communication, which could negatively impact marital peace and trust.

However, over time, there has been a shift towards more equal relationships, where communication is seen as a key component of a healthy and fulfilling marriage. This has led to the development of various communication strategies and techniques designed to improve marital intimacy and trust, such as active listening, non-defensive communication. Families that value a lot of talking believe it helps them stay close and understand each other better. They see regular communication as a key way to teach and guide their children. But families that don't talk much don't think it's necessary to share ideas or talk often in order to function well or raise their kids (Evans, 2024).

Family communication encompasses the ways spouses and children exchange information, thoughts, and emotions, either verbally or non-verbally. It involves the continuous process of sending and receiving messages between husband and wife as they engage in their marital relationship. Through communication, couples are able to understand, share, and connect on various aspects such as emotions, thoughts, past experiences, and personal challenges within and beyond the relationship. Effective family communication serves as the foundation that unites spouses, strengthens their relationship, and drives the overall functioning of the family. Peace communication, in particular, fosters courage an essential trait in any thriving marriage. It enables couples to consider and respect each other's perspectives, even in the face of external influences. Family communication involves verbal and non-verbal interactions that help in building relationships and managing family roles. It is essential in shaping emotional closeness and resolving conflicts (Johnson & Roloff, 2020).

On the other hand, Marital Peace is the result of intentional effort, mutual respect, understanding, living in harmony and emotional maturity between two people who are committed to building a lasting and meaningful marriage. Marital peace refers to the state of living in harmony, understanding one another and emotional closeness that exists between spouses. It is vital for building a strong and satisfying marriage, as it contributes to the emotional well-being and happiness of the family. He further explains that a healthy

and successful marriage depends on how husbands and wives relate to each other how well they support one another, and the level of their commitment to the relationship (Igbinoba, 2023).

6.4 Community Radio and Marital Peace

As a significant information source, community radio raises awareness and gives practical skills to rural communities. A widespread belief holds that community-based media are powerful since they provide a voice for the voiceless, give skills for empowerment and help the communities in peace resolutions (Backhaus 2020). The current study investigates the potential and limitations of Nigeria's Orisun 89.5 FM community radio project in promoting post-conflict peacebuilding. The investigation is carried out in Ile-Ife, an old Yoruba town that is regarded as the birthplace of civilization, in the suburbs. Ife is the ancestral and spiritual home of every Yoruba, according to folklore. Ile-Ife is thought to have been the starting point for the creation of the planet. Consequently, it is known as the 'Land of the Source' in common parlance. Ife Central and Ife East are the two local governments that manage Ile-Ife administratively (Osun State Government 2017).

Jallov (2012) in Emovwodo, Adedimeji, Saud & Ida (2024) reveals some importance of community radio to peacebuilding efforts by stating that community radio is crucial to: reaching most of those 'hardest to reach' regions, including those where people are living in conflict or in unstable environments, it is transistor or automobile, radio reception is portable and accessible to receivers. Radio can theoretically be heard anywhere, it is simple to manufacture radio, and it is simple to include numerous voices, including voices of individuals who are typically 'voiceless', listeners can easily access the radio and provide feedback by dialing in, sending texts or using digital services like text (SMS and other messaging systems) or voice calls and if there is political will and a local vision, radio has the potential to be a forum for public discourse and the growth of a sense of citizenship.

Community radio broadcasters are most effective in countering disinformation circulating at state or national levels since these kinds of messages are fact-checked quickly and broadcasters can locate these fact-checked reports and use it for their own programming. However, community radio broadcasters have found it challenging to effectively counter disinformation produced and circulating at the hyper-local and local levels. In some countries, broadcasters are either prohibited by law or culturally discouraged to discuss electoral politics (Balan & Norman, 2012). Clearly, disinformation in this domain is hard to challenge or counter since doing so could involve the risk of upsetting powerful political actors and the radio stations could face adverse consequences. Similar risks are involved with countering disinformation in the domain of religion or faith.

Community radio sustains marital peace by promoting dialogue, facilitating understanding, providing education on conflict resolution, and giving voice to marginalized groups, including those affected by domestic violence (Nnah, 2020). By broadcasting in local languages and addressing issues relevant to the community, such as domestic issues and cultural conflicts, community radio empowers people, offers practical solutions, and creates a supportive environment for peaceful coexistence within families and the wider society.

6.5 Review of Empirical Studies

A study conducted by Omeje, Ugwu, and Ogidi (2022), on Influence of marital communication on family stability of married teachers in Nsukka education zone. The study investigated how marital communication affects family stability among married teachers in the Nsukka Education Zone of Enugu State. The research was guided by two research questions and two hypotheses. The study targeted a population of 1,688 married secondary school teachers in the zone, from which a sample of 455 participants was selected using proportionate stratified sampling. A correlational research design was employed, and data were gathered through a questionnaire. The findings revealed a significant positive correlation ($p < 0.05$) between marital communication and family stability among the participants. Based on the results, the researchers offered

recommendations and highlighted the implications of the findings, including the suggestion that married teachers should avoid linking family issues to specific communication styles in various situations.

Awosan, and Okolo (2023) carried out a study on effects of spousal communication on marital stability and productivity in Nigeria. This study aims to determine the effects of spousal communication on marital stability and productivity in Nigeria. This research adopted the Solution Focused Theory of premarital screening and the Sound Relationship House Theory as its theoretical frameworks. A systematic review method was employed for the purpose of this research to search the major digital databases in order to locate all relevant published works that address one or more of the critical concepts examined in the paper, followed by a systematic integration and presentation of the findings.

Egharevba & Omosuvb (2021) in their study focused on the role of the extended family on marital instability in Egor Local Government Area of Edo State. The objectives were to ascertain the underlining causes of marital instability among couples and the roles the extended family system play in marital instability. The theoretical framework utilized was the Conjoint Family Counseling Theory. The study adopted a cross-sectional research design. The population comprised literate and non-literate persons aged 18 and above residing in the study area as at the time of the research and have been in marital union. The study involved 200 participants who were selected through the simple random sampling technique from an estimated population of 41,311 people in the area. Instruments of data collection include the use of a structured questionnaire and an in-depth interview guide. Findings of the study revealed that the extended family members in the study area are part and parcel of the marriages either directly or indirectly. The roles played by the extended family members in marital union impact the marital dispute or settlement depending on their standpoint. Hence, the study recommended that the extended family members work in harmony with those in a marriage relationship and make sure there is love, peace and mutual understanding between couples.

Egharevba & Omijie (2024) did a study that examined the contributing factors of marriage dissolution in Oredo Local Government, Edo State, Nigeria. The objectives studies were: to ascertain the impact of communication on marriage dissolution in Oredo Local Government Area and assess the impact of ethnicity on marriage dissolution in Oredo Local Government Area, Edo State Nigeria. The paper adopted Social Learning theory because it best explains the topic under investigation hence it was selected for the study. The study adopted the survey research design. The design was best suitable for the study because of the nature of the study. The study population included all marriage couples from 18years and above in Oredo Local government Area. This was irrespective of ethnic background, sex or colour, religion and occupation. Oredo Local Government Area has a population of 110,238 couples; Oredo also has a projected population up to the year 2021 was 534,206 couples. (The Oredo LGA statistical department) the sample size of the study was 400 using Solvin's sample size determination formula. The research established that communication lag has the tenents of fostering marriage dissolution and differences in ethnicity may also be a contributing factor that leads to marriage dissolution. Based on the findings of the study it was recommendations that: couples should participate in premarital education before getting married and the policy makers should advocate for the strengthening of marriage by reforming divorce laws to make divorce harder to obtain.

Emovwodo, Adedimeji, Saud & Ida (2024) did a study on community radio and post-conflict peace building. This study assessed the extent to which community radio has contributed to the peacebuilding efforts after the Ife–Modakeke conflict in Nigeria, by investigating to ascertain listeners' perceptions and adoption of the alternative dispute resolution (ADR) mechanism in managing the conflict to avoid a violent escalation. The study applied in-depth interviews and collected data with questionnaires. The findings of the study suggested that the inhabitants of Ife and Modakeke listened intensely to and were aware of the conflict resolution programme on one of the popular radio stations, Orisun 89.5 FM. People also used and knew others, who used the radio programme 'ADR mechanism' on the radio to resolve the conflict and avoid violent escalation. Since it was the only peacebuilding programme, the study found that this radio programme was an effective peacebuilding tool in the Ife–Modakeke society. The study recommended that such a good effort should be broadcast more often for further heightened awareness of its diverse listeners.

6.6 Theoretical Framework

This work is anchored on family system theory. The Family Systems Theory, This theory was propounded by psychiatrist Murray Bowen in the 1950s the theory is also known as family therapy. The Bowen theory posts that family members respond to each other in habitual ways, according to their roles within the family and their unspoken relationship agreements. And he understood that these behavior patterns can create balance but also may produce dysfunction. With this understanding in mind, the family systems approach helps people resolve issues in the context of the family unit. Bowen's family systems theory fosters insight into the family group dynamic, working with it to promote a stable and healthy family. Family system theory is relevant to this study because it helped families to know the importance of effective communication through a channel of community radio in maintaining peace in marriage.

7 Methodology

7.1 Research Design

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. This method is suitable as it enabled researcher to investigate the already existing situation and acquire first hand information from the respondents to solve the problem of this study.

7.2 Area of the Study and Population of the Study

This study was carried out in Edo State to ascertain the opinion of the residents on the relevance of community radio on sustaining marital peace in the State. The population size of Edo residents according to National Bureau of Statistics (2022) is 4,777,000. Edo State is situated at the South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria. It has a total of eighteen Local Government areas with three Senatorial zones and three major ethnic groups. Its capital city is Benin City.

7.3 Sample and Sampling Size Determination

To determine the sample size of the study, online Australian calculator as provide by NSS (National Statistical Service) with a confidence level of 95%, precision level of 0.05% and an estimate of variance (proportion) of 0.5% was used (NSS, 2012). The Australian calculator allows one to calculate the required responding sample size, required error, relative standard error and confidence interval (0.05), proportionate estimate, using just one of these criteria as in an input. The sample size was calculated at 385 respondents. Thereafter, cluster, stratified and simple random sampling technique were applied to select the respondents. Edo State was divided into three Senatorial zones where three Local Government Areas were selected and later narrowed to married residents from each of the three Local Government Areas.

7.4 Instrument of Data Collection and Reliability Test

The instrument used for the collection of data in this study was structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed to elicit information from the selected residents to respond to questions of this study. The questionnaire was tested for reliability and validity and was justified for this study.

7.5 Method of Data Collection and Analysis

The questionnaire copies were administered directly to the respondents. All copies filled cum data collected were coded, tabulated and analyzed using descriptive analysis method whereby frequency and simple percentage values are used the present and analyze accordingly.

8 Data Presentation and Analysis

This section of this research work deals with the presentation and analysis of data gathered through the use of questionnaire distributed to the respondents. Out of the total of three hundred and eighty five (385) copies of the questionnaire, three hundred and eighty copies (380) were filled and retrieved for analysis as presented in the tables below:

Table 1: Analysis of Respondents' Demographic Data

Sex class	Frequency	Percentage
Male	150	39.5
Female	230	60.5
Total	380	100

Age bracket	Frequency	Percentage
20 – 25 years	68	17.9
26 – 30 years	49	12.9
31 – 35 years	72	18.9
36 – 40 years	56	14.7
41 – 45 years	80	21.1
46 years and above	55	14.5
Total	380	100

Marital status	Frequency	Percentage
Active in marriage	215	56.6
Divorced after married	62	16.3
Widow/Widower	103	27.1
Total	380	100

Field survey 2025

The table above, containing the demographic profile of the respondents, shows that 150 (39.5%) of the respondents are males while 230 (60.5%) are females. Thus the majority are females. On the issue of Age, 68 (17.9%) of the respondents were at the age bracket of 20 – 25 years, 49 (12.9%) were 26 – 30 years, 72 (18.9%) were 31 – 35 years, 56 (14.7%) were 36 – 40 years, 80 (21.1%) were 41 – 45 years, while 55 (14.5%) were 46 years and above. Thus the majority were at the age of 41 – 45 years. On the issue of Marital status, 215 (56.6%) are married, 62 (16.3%) are divorced and 103 (27.1%) are widowed. Thus, the majority were actively in their marriage bond.

Data analyzed and presented in table 2 above revealed the responses of the respondents on Edo State residents' access to EBS community radio messages on marital peace in the State. Out of 380 respondents, 117 or 30.8% of them indicated that there was very regular access to the radio on marital peace talks and messages in the State, 181 or 47.7% indicated not regular access to radio on marital peace talks and messages while 63 or 16.6% indicated no access against 5.0% that indicated not interested on issues of radio and marital peace.

On the role of EBS community radio on marital peace in Edo State, data analyzed and presented in table 3 revealed that 111 or 29.2% of the respondents indicated that messages on open, honest and regular communication to each partner, 202 or 53.2% of the respondents indicated that marriage information on trust, mutual understanding and love to one another, and 58 or 15.3% on quick resolution of conflicts and understanding of individual differences while only 9 or 2.4% indicated on the use of counseling and seminars to sustain marriages in Edo State.

Responses on the effectiveness EBS community radio in sustaining marital peace in Edo State as pre-

Table 2: Responses on Edo State residents' access to EBS community radio messages on marital peace in the State

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Very regular access to the radio on marital peace talks and messages in the State	117	30.8%
Rarely or not regular access to radio on marital peace talks and messages	181	47.7%
No access or knowledge of radio messages on marital peace in the State	63	16.6%
Not interested on issues of radio and marital peace	19	5.0%
Total	380	100%

Field survey 2025

Table 3: Responses on the role of EBS community radio on marital peace in Edo State

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Messages on open, honest and regular communication to each partner	111	29.2%
Marriage information on trust, mutual understanding and love to one another	202	53.2%
Messages on quick resolution of conflicts and understanding of individual differences	58	15.3%
Application of marriage counseling and seminars for both husbands and wives	9	2.4%
Total	380	100%

Field survey 2025

Table 4: Responses on the effectiveness EBS community radio in sustaining marital peace in Edo State

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
EBS community radio is highly effective in sustaining marital peace in Edo State	29	7.6
EBS community radio is fairly or moderately effective in sustaining marital peace in Edo State	168	44.2
EBS community radio is lowly or insignificantly effective in sustaining marital peace in Edo State	120	31.5
EBS community radio is not effective at all in sustaining marital peace in Edo State	63	16.7
Total	380	100%

Field survey 2025

sented in table 4 revealed that 29 or 7.6% of them indicated highly effective, 168 or 44.2% indicated fairly or moderately effective while 120 or 31.5% indicated lowly or insignificantly effective and the last set of 63 or 16.7% indicated not effective at all.

9 Discussion of Results

In this study, the residents of Edo State selected from three Local Government Areas of the three senatorial zones were studied by seeking their opinion on the relevance of community radio (using Edo State Broadcasting Service radio station as an anchor) in sustaining marital peace in the State. The questionnaire was channeled to married men and women who gave their views on the subject matter. However, the respondents were of different age brackets and marital status of either actively in marriage, divorced or widowed. The outcome of the inquiry revealed relevant result that can be used in solving the problem of sustaining marital peace in the State.

The result of this study on the level of Edo State residents' access to EBS community radio messages on marital peace in the State, majority of the respondents indicated "rarely or not regular access to radio on marital peace talks and messages". This reveals that residents of the do not usually access the state radio station on the presentation of its special issues like maintaining marital peace. This is evidence of lack of information interest from the state radio which could be caused by one or two factors against the station or the respondents. For instance, Comrade Freeborn Ahanon on 17th December, 2024 posted in his Edo Political Forum of Facebook "Na small thing remain for Owanlen to dissolve all marriages and relationships in Edo State". The community radio ought to be the voice of the people where reliable information dissemination for community consumption and benefit should emanate from.

Contrary to this result, Suman (2024) discovers that one of the biggest strengths of a community radio is that it can initiate and promote dialogue between conflicting parties in a community, and dialogue often leads to solutions. Many times, problems remain unresolved because they are not addressed in a manner that is conducive to bringing about a reasonable conclusion. Trained local broadcasters can fill this gap through delicate handling of sensitive issues, making sure all parties are well represented and heard. Thus, community radios are meant to facilitate dialogue, and any conflict can only be addressed through dialogue to create understanding and practical solutions.

Result of question two on the role of EBS community radio on marital peace in Edo State revealed that majority of the respondents covering 53.5% indicate that marriage information on trust, mutual understanding and love to one another. Other views indicated by the respondents are use of messages on open, honest and regular communication to each partner and application of quick resolution of conflicts and understanding of individual differences. These are family peacebuilding measures that when appropriately and adequately disseminated from the right channel to the right audience would produce the desired result that will sustain marital peace in the State.

Community radio stations like EBS ought to act as neutral platforms where couples and community members can discuss sensitive issues like domestic violence, marital challenges, and differing needs, which is crucial for resolving conflicts. On the other hand, citizens of the State see the station as theirs where they can express their views, worries, concerns and opinions on important issues like marriage. For instance, through discussions programmes and the sharing of diverse perspectives, radio programs help foster mutual understanding between spouses and different groups, creating a basis for peaceful coexistence of married couples.

On the third question which sought to find out the effectiveness EBS community radio in sustaining marital peace in Edo State, majority of the respondents indicated that EBS community radio is fairly or moderately effective in sustaining marital peace in Edo State. This is followed by the 31.5% of the respondents that indicated that EBS community radio is lowly or insignificantly effective in sustaining marital peace in Edo State. The implication of this result is that Edo State Broadcasting Service which is the community radio of the State government as at time of this study was not an effective channel in sustaining marital peace in the State.

A study by Ojo & Ayobolu (2020) indicated that it is regrettably that rural broadcasting (community radio) which ought to be premised on the principles of public interest, conscience and necessity has been put on a rickety control of government or sponsorship. In spite of the fact that, their programmes that are rural oriented policy which requires airing for rural dwellers orientation, often failed to display this

responsibility. Despite the fact that community radio programmes especially in indigenous languages have the ability of integrating the rural audience into the mainstay of government rural-agenda, the impact is not strongly felt in most of the rural communities (Ojo & Ayobolu (2020). It is imperative that community radio in Edo State has much to do in this digital age where people can get their needed information at the comfort of their place and time.

10 Conclusion and Recommendations

This study investigated the relevance of community radio in sustaining marital peace in Edo State. The result revealed that in spite of high level of awareness and access to the radio station by majority of the citizens of Edo State coupled with the evidences of marital peace building messages by the station, the best has not been achieved. The contributions of the State community radio were rate between average and low. In conclusion, Edo State community radio was not an effective medium for sustaining marital peace due to some traditional, religious, information and social factors that should be addressed in line with current needs for the actualization and sustenance of peace in marriages.

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The Edo State community radio (EBS) should collaborate with other mass media especially digital cum social media in conveying or disseminating messages for sustaining marital peace in the state.
2. Professional marriage counselors, church leaders and peace communication experts should partner with community radio on communicating marital peace in Edo State.
3. The EBS community radio should seek support and sponsor via the State Government and other marriage institutions or agencies to carry out public awareness, education and sensitization campaigns in the State.

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